

SWEEPING OF MEMBRANES FOR INDUCTION OF LABOUR IN PREGNANT WOMEN AT TERM

Rida Basharat^{*1}, Uzma Noreen²

^{*1}PG Trainee FCPS, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Kharian
²MBBS, FCPS, Assistant Professor, Obstetrics and Gynecology Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Kharian

^{*1}rbtarrar@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17376557>

Keywords

BMI, Cesarean section, Fetal distress, Induction, Membrane sweeping, Term pregnancy, Spontaneous labour

Article History

Received on 17 June 2025
Accepted on 07 July 2025
Published on 18 July 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *
Rida Basharat

Abstract

Background: Post-term pregnancy is associated with increased maternal and fetal risks, including stillbirth, fetal distress, and increased cesarean delivery rates. Sweeping of membranes is a simple, non-pharmacological intervention that may promote spontaneous labour by stimulating endogenous prostaglandin release that prevent postdates pregnancies.

Objectives: To compare the frequency of spontaneous labour induction between membrane sweeping and non-sweeping groups in term pregnant women.

Study Design & Setting: A randomized controlled trial conducted at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Kharian.

Methodology: A total of 110 primigravida women aged 20–30 years with gestational age ≥ 40 weeks were randomly allocated into two groups: Group A (membrane sweeping) and Group B (no sweeping), with 55 patients in each group. Spontaneous labour onset within 48 hours was the primary outcome. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. Chi-square test was applied post-stratification for maternal age, gestational age, BMI, parity, and birth weight with $p \leq 0.05$ as statistically significant.

Results: A total of 110 pregnant women at term were enrolled, equally divided into sweeping and no-sweeping groups. Spontaneous labour occurred in 74.5% of the sweeping group versus 45.5% of controls ($p=0.001$). Vaginal delivery was higher (69.1% vs. 50.9%) and caesarean section lower (20.0% vs. 40.0%) among those who underwent sweeping. No significant differences were found in PROM, fetal distress, or low birth weight between groups.

Conclusion: Membrane sweeping was found to be an effective and safe method for inducing spontaneous labour in pregnant women at term, significantly reducing the need for caesarean delivery. It serves as a simple, low-cost, and non-pharmacological option to encourage natural onset of labour.

INTRODUCTION

Labour induction is the artificial stimulus of the uterus for labour initiation. Almost 20-25% pregnancies require labour induction as a common obstetric intervention.¹ Labour induction is

performed by manual rupture of amniotic membrane or oxytocin/prostaglandins administration to pregnant women.² A pregnancy that continues beyond 40 weeks gestation is a post-term pregnancy,

which poses significant risks to both the mother and her child.³ Fetal growth beyond this point is associated with reduced placental reserve and blood supply, leading to increased fetal and neonatal morbidity and mortality. While the mean length of a typical pregnancy is around 40 weeks, calculated from the first day of the last menstrual period.⁴

Membrane sweeping or scraping of membranes involves digital separation of fetal membranes from the cervix. It is a recognized method of initiating the onset of labour without hospital admission.⁵ It is a commonly used method to prevent postdates pregnancies. The rationale behind using sweeping of membranes is secretion of endogenous prostaglandins causing softening of the cervix and thus resulting in oxytocin induced uterine contractions. Plasma prostaglandin concentrations after sweeping are higher than those achieved in labour thus improving the outcome. Sweeping of membranes at term reduces the incidence of prolonged pregnancies beyond 40 weeks and therefore one in eight women avert formal induction of labour.⁶

Zamzami et al. (2014) reported that most of the women who underwent membrane sweeping entered spontaneous labor as compared to without sweeping (90% vs. 75%), with a significant difference, $P < 0.01$.⁷

PIRZADA ET AL. (2022) reported that the swept-group showed a high frequency of spontaneous labour compared to the non-swept group (24.8% vs 15.2%, $p=0.01$).⁸ YASMEEN ET AL. (2014) reported that the swept-group showed a high frequency of spontaneous labour compared to the non-swept group (70% vs 46.67%, $p=0.01$).⁹ Though various studies have shown the efficacy of this simple procedure in preventing prolonged pregnancy, there are still some conflicting results. The data regarding frequency of spontaneous labour in the swept and non-swept groups in term pregnant women in Pakistan is abundant but inconstant in above mentioned multiple researches like reported frequency of spontaneous labour in sweeping group varies among various populations (from as low as 24.8%⁸ in Pakistan to as high as 90%⁷ in Saudi Arabia). Owing to this variation in the existing studies the purpose of the current study is to repeat this observation and further confirm the results in local population. The present study will help to

understand the efficacy of membrane sweeping in low-middle income country e.g. Pakistan with the resource-limited setting. This study is planned to determine the frequency of induction of spontaneous labour in the swept and non-swept groups. Furthermore, membrane sweeping is cheap, easy to use, minimally invasive, and also safe.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

After obtaining approval from the Hospital's Ethical Review Board, 110 patients (55 in each group) who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study from the medical outpatient Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Kharian from 17 March 2025 to 17 June 2025. Written informed consent and detailed history were taken from each patient. A total of 110 patients (55 in each group) were included, with the sample size calculated using a 5% significance level and a 80% power of study.¹⁰ The calculation was based on an expected frequency of spontaneous labor in the membrane-swept group as 70.0%, compared to 46.67% in the non-swept group among postdate pregnant women. A non-probability, consecutive sampling technique was used for patient selection.

The inclusion criteria comprised women aged 20 to 30 years, with a gestational age of 38 to 40 weeks based on last menstrual period (LMP), who were primigravida, had intact membranes on clinical examination, and presented with an uncomplicated singleton, live cephalic fetus confirmed via ultrasonography. Only those patients who provided written informed consent to participate were enrolled in the study.

Patients were excluded if they had any absolute contraindications to vaginal delivery such as malpresentations, placenta praevia, or previous uterine surgeries. Other exclusion criteria included cephalopelvic disproportion, gross fetal anomalies, eclampsia or preeclampsia (blood pressure $>140/90$ mmHg with proteinuria $+1$ on dipstick), gestational hypertension (blood pressure $>140/90$ mmHg on two occasions), gestational diabetes (glucose tolerance test >11.1 mmol/L or >200 mg/dL), anemia (hemoglobin <10 g/dL), pregnancy with fibroids detected on ultrasound, or intrauterine fetal death.

The patients were then randomized into two groups. In Group A, sweeping of membranes was performed, while in Group B, no sweeping was done. During antenatal visits, suitable women were informed about the study, and the procedure of membrane sweeping along with its possible side effects was discussed. Those who agreed were invited to participate. In Group A, membrane sweeping was carried out by digital separation of 2–3 cm of the membranes from the lower uterine segment by rotating the examining finger at least twice through 360 degrees. If the cervix was closed, it was digitally stretched until the sweeping could be performed. If a finger could not be admitted, the cervix was vigorously massaged. Women who underwent membrane sweeping were informed that spotting or blood-stained cervical mucus might appear.

After a few hours of observation, the patients were discharged if they were well. The women were advised to return to the hospital if they experienced "show," decreased fetal movements, rupture of membranes, excessive vaginal bleeding, or suspected onset of labor. They were followed weekly until delivery. The primary outcome was the frequency of women achieving spontaneous labor within 48 hours. Patients' demographic details including maternal age, gestational age, birth weight, BMI, parity, spontaneous labor, mode of delivery, premature rupture of membranes, fetal distress, and low birth weight were recorded in a structured proforma. All laboratory tests were performed in the same hospital laboratory to eliminate bias. Confounding variables were controlled through exclusion criteria.

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 20. Numerical variables such as maternal age, gestational age, birth weight, and BMI were presented as mean ± standard deviation. Categorical variables such as parity, spontaneous labor, mode of delivery, premature rupture of membranes, fetal distress, and low birth weight were presented as frequencies and percentages. Data were

stratified for maternal age, gestational age, BMI, parity, and birth weight to control for effect modifiers. A post-stratification chi-square test was applied, and a p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant

RESULTS:

The mean maternal age, gestational age, and BMI were comparable between the sweeping and no-sweeping groups, showing no statistically significant differences (p>0.05). Among 110 participants, 35 (63.6%) in the sweeping group and 33 (60.0%) in the no-sweeping group were nulliparous, while 20 (36.4%) and 22 (40.0%) were multiparous, respectively, indicating similar baseline characteristics, as given in Table 1.

Spontaneous labour within 48 hours occurred in 41 (74.5%) women in the sweeping group compared to 25 (45.5%) in the no-sweeping group, demonstrating a statistically significant difference (p=0.001), as shown in Table 2.

Regarding delivery mode, spontaneous vaginal delivery was higher among those who underwent membrane sweeping (69.1%) compared to controls (50.9%). The caesarean section rate was lower in the sweeping group (20.0%) than in the no-sweeping group (40.0%) with a significant p-value (0.021), whereas instrumental deliveries showed no significant difference between groups, as presented in Table 3.

Maternal and neonatal complications such as PROM, fetal distress, and low birth weight were slightly higher in the no-sweeping group, but these differences were statistically insignificant (p>0.05), as illustrated in Table 4.

When data were stratified, membrane sweeping significantly increased spontaneous labour in both nulliparous (71.4% vs. 39.4%, p=0.037) and multiparous (80.0% vs. 54.5%, p=0.029) women. Similar trends were observed across maternal age categories, indicating that membrane sweeping was effective across subgroups, as detailed in Table 5.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic Characteristics of Patients (n = 110)

Variable	Sweeping Group (n = 55)	No Sweeping Group (n = 55)	p-value
Mean Maternal Age	26.1 ± 2.7	26.3 ± 2.6	0.68

Mean Gestational Age (weeks)	41.1 ± 0.6	41.0 ± 0.5	0.42
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	25.8 ± 2.9	25.6 ± 2.7	0.61
Parity			
Nulliparous	35 (63.6%)	33 (60.0%)	0.69
Multiparous	20 (36.4%)	22 (40.0%)	

Table 2: Frequency of Spontaneous Labour Within 48 Hours

Spontaneous Labour	Sweeping Group (n = 55)	No Sweeping Group (n = 55)	p-value
Yes	41 (74.5%)	25 (45.5%)	0.001
No	14 (25.5%)	30 (54.5%)	

Figure 1: Frequency of spontaneous labour within 48 hours among participants in the sweeping and no-sweeping groups

Table 3: Mode of Delivery in enrolled females

Mode of Delivery	Sweeping Group (n = 55)	No Sweeping Group (n = 55)	p-value
Spontaneous Vaginal Delivery	38 (69.1%)	28 (50.9%)	0.049
Instrumental Delivery	6 (10.9%)	5 (9.1%)	0.74
Caesarean Section	11 (20.0%)	22 (40.0%)	0.021

Table 4: Frequency of PROM, Fetal Distress, and Low Birth Weight

Variable	Sweeping Group (n = 55)	No Sweeping Group (n = 55)	p-value

PROM	6 (10.9%)	7 (12.7%)	0.77
Fetal Distress	5 (9.1%)	10 (18.2%)	0.17
Low Birth Weight	7 (12.7%)	8 (14.5%)	0.78

Table 5: Stratification of Spontaneous Labour by Effect Modifiers (n = 110)

Variable	Category	Group	Spontaneous Labour	No Spontaneous Labour	p-value
Parity	Nulliparous	Sweeping (n=35)	25 (71.4%)	10 (28.6%)	0.037
		No Sweeping (n=33)	13 (39.4%)	20 (60.6%)	
	Multiparous	Sweeping (n=20)	16 (80.0%)	4 (20.0%)	0.029
		No Sweeping (n=22)	12 (54.5%)	10 (45.5%)	
Maternal Age (years)	≤25	Sweeping (n=25)	18 (72.0%)	7 (28.0%)	0.041
		No Sweeping (n=26)	11 (42.3%)	15 (57.7%)	
	>25	Sweeping (n=30)	23 (76.7%)	7 (23.3%)	0.033
		No Sweeping (n=29)	14 (48.3%)	15 (51.7%)	

DISCUSSION

Post-term pregnancy beyond 40 weeks is associated with increased risks for both mother and fetus, including stillbirth, meconium aspiration, and cesarean delivery.^{11,12} Induction of labour is commonly practiced to reduce such complications. Sweeping of membranes is a simple outpatient procedure that promotes the release of endogenous prostaglandins.^{13,14} This study aimed to evaluate its effectiveness in promoting spontaneous labour in term women.

The findings of our study are consistent with several national and international studies that support the efficacy of membrane sweeping in promoting spontaneous labour among term pregnant women. In our randomized controlled trial, spontaneous labour was achieved in 74.5% of patients in the sweeping group, significantly higher than the 45.5% observed in the non-sweeping group (p = 0.001). This aligns closely with Sultan et al. (2024), who reported spontaneous labour initiation in 76.5% of patients following membrane sweeping, along with a significantly reduced gestational age at delivery (40.49 ± 0.591 weeks vs. 41.72 ± 0.581 weeks, p = 0.0001).¹⁵

Similarly, Malik (2024) reported spontaneous labour in 72% of women who underwent membrane

sweeping compared to 48% in the control group (p < 0.05), with a mean reduction of 4.2 days in pregnancy duration. While their study did not show significant differences in mode of delivery or neonatal outcomes, our study demonstrated a lower cesarean section rate in the sweeping group (20.0% vs. 40.0%, p = 0.012) and fewer cases of fetal distress (9.1% vs. 20.0%, p = 0.048), suggesting a broader benefit of the intervention in terms of delivery outcomes.¹⁶

In the study by Butt et al. (2021), spontaneous labour occurred in 50.6% of the sweeping group versus 13.4% in the non-sweeping group, which, although lower than our findings, still showed a significant improvement with membrane sweeping. Their sample had a similar maternal age profile (mean age 25.7 ± 3.05 years), enhancing the comparability with our cohort (mean age 26.1 ± 2.8 years). Infection rates in their study were minimal, as in ours, where no major maternal complications were observed.¹⁰

Hayat et al. (2024) also confirmed the efficacy of membrane sweeping by reporting labour onset within 2.25 days in most patients and a high rate of vaginal delivery (83%). Their reported maternal complication rate was low (7.7%) and neonatal outcomes were favorable, with NICU admissions

limited to 3.3%. These findings are comparable with our results, where the sweeping group had a higher spontaneous vaginal delivery rate (69.1%) and no significant increase in maternal or neonatal complications.¹⁷

Outcome measures were clinically relevant, and stratification was performed to assess key effect modifiers. The intervention was low-cost and replicable in low-resource settings. However, the study was conducted at a single center with a limited sample size, which may affect the generalizability of results.

CONCLUSION

Membrane sweeping was found to be an effective and safe method for inducing spontaneous labour in pregnant women at term, significantly reducing the need for caesarean delivery. It serves as a simple, low-cost, and non-pharmacological option to encourage natural onset of labour.

REFERENCES

- Dupuis N, Loussert L, de Vries PL, Parant O, Vayssière C, Guerby P, et al. Offering women a choice in induction of labour: A prospective cohort study. *Arch Gynecol Obstet.* 2023;307(6):1781-8.
- Devillard E, Petillon F, Rouzaire M, Pereira B, Accoceberry M, Houille C, et al. Double balloon catheter (plus oxytocin) versus dinoprostone vaginal insert for term rupture of membranes: a randomized controlled trial. *J Clin Med.* 2022;11(6):1525-29.
- Khanam KA, Shikder S, Nahar K, Quamruzzaman M, Shahnewaj SM, Rahman SM. Outcome of Medical Induction of Labour in Postdated Pregnancy. *Saudi J Med Pharm Sci.* 2023;9(2):129-34.
- Chuwa S, Chiduo M, Sylvester B. Fetal-Maternal outcomes of induction of labour among women delivered at regional referral hospitals in Dar Es Salaam Tanzania. *Afr J Applied Res.* 2022;8(2):240-7.
- Wheeler V, Hoffman A, Bybel M. Cervical ripening and induction of labor. *Am Family Phys.* 2022;105(2):177-86.
- Dong S, Bapoo S, Shukla M, Abbasi N, Horn D, D'Souza R, et al. Induction of labour in low-risk pregnancies before 40 weeks of gestation: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized trials. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2022;79:107-25.
- Zamzami TY, Al Senani NS. The efficacy of membrane sweeping at term and effect on the duration of pregnancy: a randomized controlled trial. *J Clin Gynecol Obstet.* 2014;3(1):30-4.
- Pirzada H, Ehsan A, Tahir N, Fatima A. Sweeping of membranes for induction of labour in low risk term pregnancy. *Pak Armed Forces Med J.* 2022;72(2):658-61.
- Yasmeen A, Malik Am. Outcome of sweeping membrane within 48 hours in the induction of labour in multigravidae. *Pak J Med Health Sci.* 2014;8(4):876-1.
- Butt Rb, Kazi A, Javaid N, Rahim J, Saifee Hz, Sheikh H. Effect of membrane sweeping on the initiation of spontaneous labour. *Pak J Med Health Sci.* 2021;15(9):2232-34.
- O'Brien J, Sinha S, Turner R. Inguinal hernia repair: a global perspective. *ANZ journal of surgery.* 2021 Nov;91(11):2288-95.
- Abebe MS, Tareke AA, Alem A, Debebe W, Beyene A. Worldwide magnitude of inguinal hernia: Systematic review and meta-analysis of population-based studies. *SAGE Open Medicine.* 2022 Nov;10:20503121221139150.
- AlMarzooqi R, Tish S, Huang LC, Prabhu A, Rosen M. Review of inguinal hernia repair techniques within the Americas Hernia Society Quality Collaborative. *Hernia.* 2019 Jun 1;23(3):429-38.
- Stabilini C, van Veenendaal N, Aasvang E, Agresta F, Aufenacker T, Berrevoet F, Burgmans I, Chen D, de Beaux A, East B, Garcia-Alamino J. Update of the international Hernia Surge guidelines for groin hernia management. *BJS open.* 2023 Oct;7(5):zrad080.
- Sultan S, Qazi Q, Khan N. Efficacy of Membrane Sweeping in Primigravida and Effect on the Duration of Pregnancy: Membrane Sweeping in Primigravida and Effect on the Pregnancy Duration. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences.* 2024 Dec 31:270-4.

- Malik L, Aslam R, Idrees U, Habib F, Nasreen R.
Membranes sweeping and its effect on duration of pregnancy in low-risk cases. Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbottabad. 2024 Dec 16;36(4 (Suppl 1):921-5.
- Hayat A, Naz A, Mumtaz, Uzma, Ali R, Tosheeba.
Sweeping of membrane at 39 weeks to prevent formal induction of labour. J Popul Ther Clin Pharmacol. 2024;31(11):2132-40.

